

THE MAIN TASKS OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES OF STUDENTS AT THE UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: Research work of students is one of the most important forms of the educational process. Being engaged in research activities, the student develops independence of judgment, the ability to defend his point of view, as well as creative thinking.

Keywords: Research work, motivation, educational process, professional training, independence, students.

Science is only a science when it does not regulate and does not bind itself with the question of immediate benefit. The research activity that complements the educational process includes the scientific work of students, which implies their independent activity outside the framework of curricula and training plans.

Science laboratories, circles and seminars allow the student to start their research work. The research work of students is an important factor in the preparation of a young specialist and scientist, because the student himself acquires skills that will be useful to him throughout his life, and in particular in his professional activity.

In my opinion, the participation of teachers is important in research work. The necessary assistance and attention to the work of students should be provided. It is important to show students' interest in scientific activities. It is also important to encourage students for research work. Students should feel motivated and useful in scientific work.

Scientific (research) activity - activities aimed at obtaining and applying new knowledge.

Research activities, complementing the educational process, include the scientific work of students, implying their independent activity outside the framework of curricula and training plans. Scientific (Research) activity - activities aimed at obtaining and applying new knowledge

In modern conditions, the role of scientific knowledge in all spheres of social life is significantly increasing, attention is increasing to the problems of the

development of the Academy of Sciences, its modernization. New scientific knowledge in institutions of higher education, act as an important sector of science and progress in the country.

Speaking about the peculiarities of scientific activity, it is necessary to distinguish between individual scientific activity - as a process of scientific work of an individual researcher - and collective scientific activity - as the activity of the entire community of scientists working in a given branch of science, or as the work of the research team of a research institute, scientific groups, scientific schools and etc.

The main goal of students' research activities is to obtain in-depth knowledge in certain areas of science and technology, as well as to acquire practical skills in their future profession.

The main tasks of organizing and developing the system of research activities of students in universities at the present stage are:

- ensuring the dialectical connection of the educational process and preparing students for creative scientific and pedagogical activities;
- the formation of an environment beneficial for the manifestation and implementation of the personal creative potential of representatives of student youth;
- the transformation of students' research work into a massive and highly productive activity;
- search for talented youth with abilities and interest in scientific and pedagogical activities;
- education and development of students' personal and professional qualities necessary for the successful implementation of scientific and scientific - pedagogical activities;
- rationalizing the free time of student youth, distracting them from acquiring bad habits and antisocial aspirations.

Scientific (research) activity - activities aimed at obtaining and applying new knowledge. Factors conditioning the actualization of students' research activities at the university. The reasons why students are engaged in research activities are:

The reasons why students are engaged in research activities can be represented. In the case of scientific activity, the inner motivation for it is pleasure, satisfaction obtained from the process of work itself, the desire for intellectual success, the desire to solve and find problems, to give work to the mind. The basis of a person's scientific activity is his motivational sphere as a set of personality motives and the most important characteristic of his suitability for scientific work.

The types of rewarding students for success in their studies and research activities include:

- Set-off of the results of research work of students;
- Providing recommendations for further training and internships;
- Providing the opportunity to graduate in a shorter period of time;
- Early passing of exams and tests;
- Participation in special classes for the most capable and talented students.

Only one third of the students are engaged in research work at the university. Scientific research is optional, which is carried out in free time from the main work. This attitude is shaped by several circumstances.

Participation of students in scientific research for enterprises and organizations, in all-Russian student scientific events, in competitions for grants is rather an exception to the rule.

The most significant problems for students in research work at the university are:

- Lack of funding for scientific research;
- Material incentives for subjects of research activities;
- The problem of postgraduate employment;
- Lack of social benefits as a reward for scientific activity;
- Lack of opportunity to introduce student scientific developments into production;
- Lack of regular scientific contacts with Russian and foreign universities, internships in Russian and foreign universities;
- Inability to publish student papers.
- Intrinsic motivation prevails, i.e. a person includes activity for its own sake, and not for the sake of other goals, in relation to which it is a means of achieving them.

In order to activate and improve the effectiveness of the system of research activities of students, it is necessary to expand the use of the most effective types of educational, material and moral stimulation of students, scientific and pedagogical, scientific and other personnel of the university.

A small percentage of students are engaged in research activities in universities. It is necessary to pay attention to the majority and attract as many students as possible to scientific work, because talented and capable students who have not had time to become interested in research work can go to the ranks of the majority.

In my opinion, the problem of non-participation of students in scientific activities is conditioned by many factors. For example, lack of information, lack of time, besides, there is no clear goal for doing scientific work, except for its own sake, but the leading factor of non-participation in scientific activity, I believe, is the laziness of students, because many of them are talented in their own way.

Therefore, after analyzing the problem, I concluded that in the universities of our country students are engaged in research activities at will, for the sake of the idea itself. Perhaps science cannot be dealt with in another way and no incentives, such as money, credits, etc. will not help students become perhaps more inventive and creative.

Consequently, students who strive for self-improvement are engaged in scientific activities.

List of references

1. Anderson N. J., Exploring Second Language Reading: Issues and Strategies. – Boston, 1999 - 129 p.
2. Almatova N.A. Development Of Design Skills And Abilities At Foreign Language Lessons. Economy and society. № 11(78) -s.: 2020.
3. Mamajonov I, Alijonova M, Qambarov A, Mamatov R «Opportunities of eastern thinkers on improving the preparation of the future economist for innovative activity» Journal of critical reviews. 2020.
4. Egamberdiyeva D.U. Methods of using computer technology in the process of teaching English. International scientific journal. Economy and society. № 6(73) - s.: 2020.
5. G.T. Qodirova. Linguistic and communicative competence in learning language. International conference., 2016, p.441.
6. N.A. Odilova., M.U. Irgashev. Information and communication technology in language learning. International conference., 2016, p.439.
7. Usmonova Sh. Study of scientific technical transfusion in non-linguistic educational university. International journal. Moscow.2019.
8. Mukhitdinova F.R. Creative qualities of the students in the system of higher education. //Economy And Society. № 11(78) -S.: 2020